

Ionomer: release of ions and monomers

Glass particles: reinforces the material's structure

Presentation: powder + liquid, capsules (must have a shaker), paste

Classification:

- Conventional
- Reinforced by metals
- Modified by resin

Conventional:

Powder (silica, alumina, calcium fluoride, aluminum, sodium and aluminum fluoride).

Liquid: water (to ionize the monomers), polyacrylic acid (main component, responsible for the adhesion of the powder to the liquid/chemical reaction in the formation of setting), Co-polymer (greater reactivity and gelling tendency (hardening of the material) and tartaric acid (longer working time, it reduces setting time, the material gels faster and the viscosity is regulated).

Setting reaction (acid-base reaction) - Gelling: 3 phases

1 phase: ionization of acids occurs, that is, the displacement of ions with the mixture of powder and liquid. (surface shine - 4min).

2 phase: the formation of the polyacid matrix occurs (increase in viscosity)

3rd phase: the formation of silica gel and final setting occurs when the glass is incorporated into the matrix.

Prey reaction:

Initial setting: 4-8 min requires surface protection to prevent imbibition and syneresis.

Imbibition - occurs in the first 4 minutes (the material is sensitive to water gain)

Syneresis - Occurs after 4-8 minutes (the material becomes sensitive to water loss). After 8 min, silica gel forms.

Final setting: 24-48 hours material acquires final strength

Advantages: excellent chelation (chemical adhesion to dentin and enamel), easy and quick manipulation, fluoride release, coefficient of linear thermal expansion similar to that of teeth, biocompatibility.

Disadvantages: high solubility/surface roughness, sensitive to water/low tensile and wear resistance, short working time and long setting time.

- Indication: base and lining, cementation, class V, restoration of primary teeth, sealant, atraumatic restorative treatment.

- Contraindication: large restorations, occlusal load, aesthetics.

GIC reinforced by metals: (conventional GIC + amalgam mesh alloy)
liquid + powder

Indication: class I deciduous and filling cores

- NOTE: this material is rarely used, as the only advantage compared to conventional GIC is mechanical resistance.

Resin-modified GIC (with resin monomers + polymerization agents).

Indication: base and lining, cementation, non-carious lesions, conservative class I, sealant.

Note: Resin-modified GIC is indicated in 3 situations: -type I: cementation, type II: restoration and type III: type IV lining/base modified by resin.

Advantages: Control of working time, shorter setting time, greater color stability, better aesthetics, Lower solubility, lower sensitivity to water, greater resistance, Chemical bonding to the composite resin.

Disadvantages: Less fluoride release, polymerization contraction, less adhesiveness.

- Handling: CIV powder + liquid

- 1 measure of powder: 1 drop of liquid. Divide the powder into two portions: 1st: mix in 15 seconds. 2nd spatular in 15 seconds. NOTE: Total spatulation is 30 seconds. Agglutinate and don't spatulate!!